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Original Research Article

IMPACT OF FINANCIAL DEEPENING ON MANUFACTURING SECTOR IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study explored the impact of financial deepening on manufacturing sector in Nigeria using time series data covering 1990 to 2023. Manufacturing sector performance is expressed by growth in manufacturing with financial access, financial depth and financial efficiency serving as indices for financial deepening. The study adopted the ex-post facto research design because of its unique attribute of being able to deal with outcome of events that have already occurred. The technique of data analysis is auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL). The findings showed that financial access and financial depth are positive and significant to growth in the manufacturing sector, while financial efficiency was negative and significant to growth in the sector. The study concludes that financial deepening contributed to growth in the manufacturing sector within the period reviewed. It therefore recommends that monetary authorities especially the CBN should implement policies that promote and increase financial depth in the society. Financial institutions such as commercial banks and micro finance banks should be encouraged to increase lending to both SMEs and manufacturing firms so as to boost productivity in the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: Financial deepening, manufacturing sector; Manufacturing sector; and ARDL

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Financial deepening refers to the process of increasing financial services and products available to individuals and businesses in an economy. This can include expanding the availability of banking services, credit facilities, insurance products, and investment opportunities, (Ohwofasa & Aiyedogbon, 2013). Financial deepening is important for economic growth as it allows for increased savings, investment, and risk management, ultimately leading to a more efficient allocation of resources in the economy. Nigeria as a country has made progress in financial deepening in recent years, with efforts to increase access to banking services, improve credit availability, and enhance financial inclusion. Financial deepening could also mean the process in which organizations and financial markets assist the exchange of goods and services, savings mobilization from investors, acquisition of information from the companies and the potential investment and hence, the allocation of public savings for production purposes (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 2005).

Financial deepening is seen also as the

process of expanding and improving financial services and products available in an economy. In the context of Nigeria, financial deepening in the manufacturing sector can have a significant impact on its growth and development. A deeper and more efficient financial system can provide the necessary funding, investment opportunities, and risk management tools that manufacturing firms need to expand and modernize their operations. Access to credit, insurance, and other financial services can help manufacturers to invest in new technologies, improve productivity, and compete more effectively in both domestic and international markets. Schumpeter (1911) stated that financial development is closely related to industrialization.

Adebayo (2010) defined manufacturing firms as industries involved in the processing and manufacturing of new commodities with value addition. The manufacturing sector in Nigeria has long been recognized as a critical driver of economic growth and industrial development. However, despite its potential, the sector has faced numerous challenges that have hampered its

growth and competitiveness. One of the key issues affecting the manufacturing sector is the limited access to finance and the shallowness of the financial system in Nigeria. Financial deepening, characterized by the expansion and sophistication of financial services, has been identified as a critical factor in supporting the growth and development of industries, including manufacturing firms. However, the extent to which financial deepening has positively impacted the manufacturing sector in Nigeria remains unclear.

McKinnon & Shaw (1973) argue that financial development leads economic growth. The observations are that financial deepening and savings increase investments in the manufacturing sector thus, stimulating economic growth. Additionally, financial deepening can also foster innovation and entrepreneurship in the manufacturing sector by providing access to venture capital, investors, and other forms of financial support for startups and small businesses. The manufacturing sector, if well developed, is a major driver of growth in any economy. The contribution of the financial system towards the growth of the manufacturing sector is

mainly credited to its mediation role of deposit mobilization and allocation of resources from the surplus to the deficit sectors of the economy (Nwakoby&Ananwude, 2016)

However, in Nigeria, it is quite disappointing that the sector has been performing below expectation, leading to decrease in industrial output, which has caused the sector to contribute less than 5% to the Gross Domestic Product (Udoh and Ogbuagu, 2012). The manufacturing sector contributed about 13% to the Nigeria GDP in 2023. And the Nigerian government has implemented policies such as the Nigerian industrial revolution plan and the economic recovery growth plan (ERGP) to promote industrialization, (World Bank Annual Report 2023) Additionally, ill-treated and malfunctioning of the sector, as a result of limited access to finance, inadequate investment and innovation, infrastructure challenges, power supply challenges, obsolete infrastructure, security challenges, smuggling and massive importation of finished products, have been the major challenges that have impeded the growth of the sector.

Overall, promoting financial deepening in Nigeria's manufacturing sector is

essential for driving economic growth, creating jobs, and diversifying the economy away from its heavy reliance on oil. Policymakers, financial institutions, and industry stakeholders should work together to strengthen the financial system, enhance access to finance for manufacturers, and create a business-friendly environment that supports sustainable growth and development in the sector. Financial system has always played a vital role in supporting economic programs and activities. Sanusi (2010), observed that a well-functioning financial system is able to mobilize domestic savings, allocate resources optimally, efficiently diversify risk, enhance the flow of liquidity, reduce information asymmetry and transaction cost. These functions therefore, suggest that financial system is expected to play a critical role in promoting manufacturing sector growth, economic growth and development.

Ezu, Okoh and Okoye (2017), opined that the high rate of growth and stability obtainable in developed nations can be attributed to the reforms undertaken in their financial system overtime. In Nigeria, the government and financial institutions have seen the need to

continue investing in infrastructure, technology, and financial education initiatives. Improving regulatory frameworks and addressing issues such as corruption and political instability will also be crucial in fostering a more robust and inclusive financial system in the country. In Nigeria, financial deepening has been a priority for the government and financial institutions in recent years. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has implemented various initiatives to promote financial inclusion and expand access to financial services, especially in underserved areas and among marginalized populations.

The introduction of mobile banking, agent banking, and other digital financial services has significantly improved financial access for many Nigerians. In Nigeria, there has been a significant growth in the financial sector over the years leading to a substantial financial deepening. For example, there is a significant progress in increasing financial inclusion, with the percentage of adults with access to financial services increasing from 21.6% in 2010 to 68.2% in 2023. Credit to the Private Sector rose from 5.3trillion Naira in 2010 to 43.07 trillion naira in 2023 and number of active

accounts rose from 65 million in 2016 to 151 million in 2022 while number of automated teller machines (ATMs) increased from 12.7million in 2013 to 17.6 million 2022 (CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2023). Despite this progress, financial deepening in Nigeria still faces challenges. Many people are still excluded from the formal financial system, with a large percentage of the population unbanked or under banked. This limits their access to credit, insurance, and other financial tools necessary for economic growth and empowerment

Sequel to the performance of the financial sector in Nigeria coupled with the identified challenges militating against the growth of the manufacturing sector and the fact that the financial sector has a prominent role to play in manufacturing activities as suggested by Rajan and Zingale (1996), the study aims to examine the impact of financial deepening on manufacturing sector in Nigeria and also find out if long run relationship exist between the financial sector and the manufacturing sector.

1.2 Problem Statement

The manufacturing sector plays a crucial role in driving economic growth and

creating employment opportunities, (Ojo, 2010). However, many developing countries including Nigeria continue to face challenges in achieving sustainable growth in this sector. One of the key issues identified is the lack of financial deepening, which refers to the availability and accessibility of financial services that are essential for businesses to thrive. Therefore, the lack of financial deepening in the manufacturing sector poses a significant obstacle to its growth and sustainability. Addressing this issue requires policymakers and stakeholders to implement strategies that promote financial inclusion, enhance access to credit, and improve financial literacy among manufacturers. (Ogunsakin, 2014).By doing so, Nigeria can unlock the potential of the manufacturing sector and stimulate economic growth in the long run. Olanrewaju, A. and Aiyegbusi (2015) conducted a study on the impact of banking sector reforms on the output of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Their findings show that the effects of Bank assets, lending rate, exchange rate and interest rate on manufacturing output were positive and significant to the growth of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. They concluded that

the effects of banking sector reforms on the output growth of manufacturing sector were significantly impacting on the economy. Despite the importance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria's economic development, the lack of financial deepening poses a significant barrier to its growth. Manufacturing firms in Nigeria face challenges in accessing affordable credit, investment capital, and financial services, leading to constrained operational capacity, limited technological advancement, and reduced competitiveness in the global market, (Obamuyi, Edun and Kayode 2012). This study seeks to investigate the impact of financial deepening on the growth and sustainability of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, identify the key barriers and constraints hindering financial access for manufacturers, and propose policy recommendations to enhance financial inclusion, access to credit, and overall financial deepening to promote the growth of the manufacturing sector in the country.

1.3 Objectives

The main aim of this study was to examine the effect of financial deepening on manufacturing growth in Nigeria

between 1990 and 2023. Specifically, the study was design to:

- i. examine the effect of financial depth (FD) on manufacturing growth in Nigeria.
- ii. establish the effect of financial access (FA) on manufacturing growth in Nigeria.
- iii. ascertain the effect of financial efficiency (FE) on manufacturing growth in Nigeria

1.4 Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses for this study are stated in the null forms as follows:

- i. H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between financial depth (FD) and manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.
- ii. H_{02} : Financial access (FA) does not significantly affect manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.
- iii. H_{03} : Financial efficiency (FE) does not have any significant effect on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 The concept of financial

deepening

Financial deepening refers to the process of improving and expanding the financial system in an economy, increasing access to financial services, and promoting greater financial inclusion and improved efficiency in the allocation of resources (CBN Statistical bulletin 2023). Financial deepening plays a critical role in promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, and enhancing financial stability within an economy. By expanding access to finance, more people and businesses, especially low-income individuals and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), are able to have easy access to financial services. Financial deepening also entails development of new financial products, such as loans, savings accounts, insurance, and investment options, as well as the expansion of financial institutions and networks (Ohwofasa & Aiyedogbon, 2013). Financial deepening is important because it can lead to: Economic growth, poverty reduction, increased financial stability, improved access to credit and other financial services, improved financial inclusion as well as increased competition and innovation. Financial deepening in Nigeria has made

significant progress, with increased financial inclusion, improved access to financial services, and increased credit to the private sector. However, challenges such as infrastructure deficits, regulatory challenges, financial literacy, and security concerns need to be addressed to further deepen the financial system in Nigeria. Some of the key initiatives and developments contributing to financial deepening in Nigeria include:

1. Financial Sector Reform: The Nigerian government has implemented various reforms aimed at strengthening the financial sector, including the recapitalization of banks and the establishment of the Asset Management Corporation of Nigeria (AMCON).
2. Payment System Development: The development of electronic payment systems, such as the Nigerian Interbank Settlement System (NIBSS), has improved the efficiency of payment transactions.
3. Mobile Money: The introduction of mobile money services has expanded financial inclusion and increased access to financial services.
4. Microfinance: The growth of microfinance institutions has provided financial services to small and medium-

sized enterprises (SMEs) and low-income individuals.

5. Capital Market Development: The development of the Nigerian capital market has provided a platform for companies to raise capital and invest in growth.

6. Financial Inclusion Initiatives: Initiatives such as the National Financial Inclusion Strategy have aimed to increase access to financial services for underserved populations.

7. Digital Banking: The adoption of digital banking services has improved access to financial services and increased financial inclusion.

8. Financial Literacy: Efforts to improve financial literacy have empowered individuals and businesses to make informed financial decisions.

9. Regulatory Framework: The development of a robust regulatory framework has helped to ensure the stability and soundness of the financial system.

10. Infrastructure Development: Investments in infrastructure, such as payment systems and financial markets infrastructure have supported financial deepening.

These initiatives and developments have

contributed to financial deepening in Nigeria by increasing access to financial services, improving the efficiency of payment systems, and promoting financial inclusion.

2.1.2 The concept of financial inclusion

Financial inclusion refers to the access and usage of financial services by individuals and businesses, particularly those who are traditionally underserved or excluded from the formal financial system, (Michael A. Goldberg, 2015). This includes access to basic banking services, savings and credit facilities, insurance products, and payment systems, (Onaolapo, 2015). Financial inclusion aims to ensure that all members of society have the ability to participate in the economy, manage their finances, and plan for the future. By promoting financial inclusion, countries are able to reduce poverty, promote economic stability, and foster inclusive growth. Financial inclusion is also termed as the extent to which individuals and businesses have access to and actively use financial services such as bank accounts, credit, insurance, and savings products, (Nwanne, 2015). Improved financial

inclusion can lead to greater economic empowerment, poverty reduction, and overall economic development. Financial inclusion indicators include metrics such as:

1. Access to formal financial services: This indicator looks at the percentage of the population that has access to formal banking services, such as bank accounts, mobile money, or other financial institutions.
2. Usage of financial services: This indicator measures how actively individuals and businesses use financial services, including the frequency of transactions, savings, credit, and insurance coverage.
3. Financial literacy and awareness: This indicator assesses the level of knowledge and understanding of financial products and services among the population, which is essential for making informed financial decisions.
4. Digital financial services adoption: This indicator tracks the usage of digital channels such as mobile banking, online payments, and electronic transfers, which can increase financial access and convenience.
5. Regulatory environment: This indicator evaluates the regulatory framework

governing financial services, including consumer protection measures, licensing requirements, and policies promoting financial inclusion.

2.1.3 The Concept of financial depth

Robert Cull (2014) defines financial depth as the size and complexity of the financial system and the level of financial services, products, and institutions available within the country. It indicates the extent to which individuals and businesses have access to various financial instruments and services, such as savings and checking accounts, credit facilities, insurance products, and investment opportunities. Shaw (1973) opined that financial depth is the accumulation of financial assets at a faster pace than the accumulation of production and non-financial wealth. A deeper financial system would offer a wider range of financial products and services, allowing for more efficient capital allocation, increased savings and investment, and better risk management. It also reflects the extent to which financial institutions are well-developed, regulated, and able to support economic activities and growth within the country. Improving financial depth can help drive economic development and prosperity by

providing individuals and businesses with the necessary tools to manage their finances effectively. World Bank defined financial depth as the increase in the stock of financial assets. In other words, financial depth means the ability of financial institutions to effectively mobilize financial resources for economic growth and development, (Sharqi, 2021). Financial depth indicators include:

1. Domestic credit to the private sector as a percentage of GDP: This indicator measures the amount of credit provided by financial institutions to the private sector relative to the size of the economy.
2. Broad money supply (M2) as a percentage of GDP: This indicator represents the total amount of money circulating in the economy relative to the size of the economy.
3. Ratio of liquid liabilities (M3) to GDP: This indicator measures the liquidity of financial assets in the economy.
4. Depth of the financial system index: This indicator combines various measures, such as the size of the banking sector, stock market capitalization, and bond market size, to provide a comprehensive measure of financial depth.

2.1.4 The concept of financial access

Financial access refers to the ability of individuals and businesses to access and utilize financial services and products to manage their finances and support economic activities. This includes services such as savings and checking accounts, credit facilities, insurance products, and investment opportunities. Demircuc-Kunt and Levine (2008) saw financial access as the absence of price and non-price barriers to finance. Claessens (2006) described financial access as availability and supply of quality financial services at realistic costs, where reasonable quality and reasonable cost have to be defined relative to some objective standard, with costs reflecting all financial and non-pecuniary costs. Implied by these definitions, financial access is the absence of obstacles to potential bank users in their pursuit to enjoying banking services and instruments, (James Lothian 2019). While there have been improvements in financial access in Nigeria in recent years, we still have challenges of portion of the population, especially in rural and underserved areas, still lack access to basic financial

services. Factors such as high poverty levels, inadequate infrastructure, low levels of financial literacy, and limited availability of banking facilities contribute to the low financial access in the country. Efforts by government to improve financial access in Nigeria include initiatives to expand banking infrastructure, promote financial inclusion through mobile and digital banking solutions, and increase financial education and literacy programs. Policy interventions and regulatory reforms aimed at reducing barriers to entry for financial institutions and promoting innovation in the financial sector can also help to enhance financial access for all Nigerians.

Financial access indicators are metrics used to assess the extent to which individuals and businesses have access to and use formal financial services. These indicators help measure the level of financial inclusion in a country and evaluate the effectiveness of policies aimed at expanding access to financial services. Common financial access indicators include:

1. Percentage of adults with a bank account: This indicator measures the proportion of the adult population that

has access to formal banking services, such as savings and checking accounts.

2. Percentage of adults with a loan from a financial institution: This indicator shows the percentage of adults who have borrowed from formal financial institutions, such as banks or credit unions.

3. Number of bank branches or ATMs per capital: This indicator measures the availability of physical banking infrastructure in a country, reflecting the ease of access to banking services for the population.

4. Percentage of adults using mobile money: This indicator reflects the adoption of mobile financial services, such as mobile money, as a means of accessing banking and payment services.
5. Credit to GDP ratio: This indicator compares the volume of credit provided by financial institutions to the size of the economy, highlighting the depth of financial intermediation in the country.

2.1.5 The Concept of financial efficiency

Financial efficiency refers to the effectiveness and productivity of the financial system in allocating resources,

facilitating transactions, managing risks, and supporting economic activities within the country (Franklin Allen 2013). A financially efficient system is characterized by well-functioning financial markets, institutions, and infrastructure that enable optimal capital allocation and resource utilization. In Nigeria, challenges to financial efficiency include issues such as high transaction costs, low levels of financial literacy, limited access to credit, inadequate regulatory frameworks, and a lack of transparency and accountability in the financial sector. These challenges can hinder the efficient functioning of the financial system and impede economic growth and development.

Efforts to improve financial efficiency in Nigeria involve implementing reforms to enhance the regulatory environment, promote competition and innovation in the financial sector, strengthen institutional capacity, and foster financial inclusion. Financial Efficiency Indicators include:

1. Return on Assets (ROA): This indicator measures the profitability of financial institutions by calculating the ratio of net income to total assets.
2. Cost-to-income ratio: This indicator

evaluates the efficiency of financial institutions by comparing operating expenses to total income.

3. Non-performing loans (NPL) ratio: This indicator measures the proportion of loans that are not being repaid on time, indicating the quality of asset management and risk assessment by financial institutions.

4. Turnover ratio: This indicator assesses the efficiency of the stock market by comparing the trading volume to market capitalization.

2.1.6 Financial Deepening and Growth in Manufacturing Sector.

Financial deepening and growth in Nigeria's manufacturing sector are interrelated and play a critical role in the country's overall economic growth and development. Financial deepening refers to the process by which financial systems in a country become more sophisticated and accessible, leading to increased financial intermediation and services. This can have a significant impact on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, as improved access to finance can help support the growth and development of businesses in this sector. Calderon and Liu, (2003), opined that a well-structured

financial sector deepening in any economy has the ability to provide financial services that could increase the level of advancement in the manufacturing sector thus paving way for investors to take advantage of the new opportunities created.

Efforts towards financial deepening in Nigeria's manufacturing sector have been made through various ideas and programs designed to increasing access to finance for manufacturers, promoting investment in manufacturing sector, and enhancing financial inclusion among populace. The manufacturing sector, if well developed, is a major driver of economic growth in any economy. Nevertheless, in Nigeria, it is quite regrettable that the sector has performed below expectation, leading to decrease in industrial output, which has caused the sector to contribute less than five percent (5%) to the Gross Domestic Product (Udoh and Ogbuagu, 2012).

Some key factors that contribute to financial deepening in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria include:

1. Improved access to finance: Financial deepening has led to increased availability of credit and financing options for manufacturing businesses in

Nigeria, allowing them to invest in new equipment, expand their operations, and improve their production processes.

2. Enhanced financial services: As financial systems become more sophisticated, manufacturing companies in Nigeria now benefit from a wider range of financial services, such as risk management, insurance, and trade finance, which can help them, navigate challenges and opportunities in the market.

3. Increased investment and innovation: With better access to finance, manufacturing businesses in Nigeria can now attract more investment, both domestic and foreign, which can fuel innovation and technological advancements in the sector, leading to increased productivity and competitiveness.

4. Strengthened supply chains: Improved access to finance has also help strengthen the supply chains of manufacturing companies in Nigeria, allowing them to access raw materials and other inputs more easily and reliably, leading to increased efficiency and cost savings.

Overall, financial deepening plays a crucial role in driving growth in the

manufacturing sector in Nigeria, by providing businesses with the resources and support they need to expand, innovate, and compete effectively in the global market.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

This section reviews supply-leading theory and demand-following theory. This study is however, anchored on the supply leading theory.

2.2.1 Supply - Leading Theory

Schumpeter (1911), in his supply-leading hypothesis emphasizes the role of a well developed financial system in promoting economic growth and innovation. According to the theory, financial deepening occurs when there is an increase in the size and complexity of the financial sector, leading to a greater availability of financial services and instruments. The supply-leading theory asserted that financial deepening brings about access to credit that is essential for entrepreneurship and economic growth. Subsequently, in an empirical study, Kayode Olawale Femi et al (2020) examined the effect of financial deepening on manufacturing firms in Nigeria, using financial deepening indicators of credit to private sector (% of GDP); market capitalization

(% of GDP); and foreign direct investment, the study concludes that financial deepening has significant effect on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria.

Following supply-leading hypothesis, King and Levine (1993) tested for the causal relationship between financial deepening and economic growth; the study found that, financial deepening triggers economic growth. On the same theoretical basis, Onwumere et al (2012) found that, broad money velocity (M2) and market liquidity (trade values of shares/GDP) had significant positive effects on economic growth in Nigeria. Also, Jolaiya, Olatubosun Felix (2024), discovered that broad money supply, private sector credits, and stock market capitalization have significant positive impact on domestic investment and economic growth. In addition, Okafor et al (2021) found that financial deepening indicators, particularly bank-based financial depth have a favorable and significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Following the supply leading hypothesis, financial deepening is expected to stimulate economic growth.

2.2.2 Demand-Following Hypothesis

Robinson (1952) asserted in his

demand-following finance hypothesis that it is economic growth and development that stimulates financial development in the economy. This hypothesis believed that financial development is endogenously determined by the real economy. This means that, the demand for financial services and assets occurred as a result of economic growth. Calderon & Liu (2003) opined that increasing financial services demand deepens the financial sector as the economy progresses. This implies that when societies promote economic growth; financial development will automatically follow. However, this view is regarded as a temporary situation that may persist only under special circumstances, such as transition to a market economy (Blum, Federmaier, Fink & Haiss, 2002). The demand-following hypothesis opines that the real sector such as manufacturing sector drives financial sector development in most economy. The demand following theory justifies that it is economic growth that motivates the creation of financial institutions in an economy. Odhiambo (2009) asserted that real sector growth induces financial services demand which is satisfied by

new financial institutions creation. Patrick (1966) concludes that the supply-leading hypothesis works in the early developmental stages in an economy, then fades out as the economy grows paving way to the demand following hypothesis.

2.3 Empirical Literature:

1. Obunike-Ezeuli, A., Ifionu, E. P. & Omojefe, G. O. (2024) examined the link between financial deepening and poverty reduction in Nigeria, using time series data from 1994 to 2022. The study adopted financial deepening indicators of Ratio of Money to National Income (MNI), financial Accessibility Ratio (FAC) and National interest Margin (NIM). Auto regressive distributive lag mode was use in the empirical analysis. Their findings showed that the Ratio of Money to National Income (MNI) has a positive relationship with poverty level. The small positive coefficient of the Financial Accessibility Ratio (FAC) emphasizes quality over quantity in financial access. Interest Margin (NIM) was found to have a positive and significant impact, stressing the importance of efficiency and competition within the financial sector. Based on the findings, the study

thus recommends that financial institutions and policymakers should develop and implement long-term strategies focusing on financial deepening to ensure poverty reduction.

2. Laminu Mamadi Mohammed and Hamsatu Musa (2024) conducted a study on the impact of financial deepening on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria from 1996 to 2022; using Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model and Bounds Tests for the data analysis. The study employed financial deepening indicators of credit to private sector and broad money supply as a ratio of GDP. The findings showed that credit to private sector by banks has significant effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. The study concludes that financial deepening has a significant effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. The study recommends that monetary authority especially the CBN should implement policies that will encourage and improve credit availability by banks to the private sector.

3. _____Jolaiya, Olatubosun Felix (2024) explored the effect of financial deepening on domestic investment in Nigeria using data from

2005 to 2022. The dependent variables for the study were financial deepening indicators of broad money supply, private sector credits, and stock market capitalization. The independent variable was domestic investment. The study used ex post facto research design and employed the ARDL technique to analyze the data. The findings revealed that broad money supply has significant positive impact on domestic investment; private sector credit has significant positive impact on domestic investment; and stock market capitalization has positive significant impact on domestic investment. The study recommended that monetary authority including CBN to implement policy that will encourage banks to improve lending to the private sector and also to increase the level of money supply in the economy.

4. Princewill Ihenacho Wachukwu, Marshal Iwedi, & Chituru Wike (2023) evaluates the relationship between financial sector deepening and economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1960 to 2021. Economic growth was proxy by real GDP while financial deepening indicators adopted in the study include: financial sector credit, financial sector liquidity and financial

market capitalization. Descriptive analytical tools or techniques were used in analyzing the data. The study concludes that financial deepening indicators of financial sector credit, financial sector liquidity and financial market capitalization have long run relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

5. Okeke, I. C. & Akunna, R. C. (2023) investigated the impact of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigerian from 1986 to 2020. Financial deepening was proxy by ratio of money supply to GDP, insurance premiums to GDP, Stock market capitalization to GDP and private sector credit to GDP, while economic growth was expressed by real GDP. The study adopted ordinary Least Square regression and ex-post facto research design in conducting the research. The findings showed that money supply to GDP and Market capitalization to GDP have positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria, while private sector credit to GDP and insurance premiums to GDP ratio had negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommends that credit to private sectors should be channeled to the productive

sector of the economy so as to boost economic growth.

6. Teacher Abdel Sattar Raef Hassan. (2023) assessed the effect of financial deepening on the economic growth of Iraq from 2004 to 2021; using auto regressive distributive lag model for the empirical analysis. The study used independent variables of liquidity ratio, credit to the private sector, net interest rate margin, trading volume and stock turnover rate. The dependent variable was expressed by real GDP. The findings showed that indicators like trading volume, stock turnover rate, and net interest rate margin all have negative impact, while the indicator of liquidity ratio, credit to the private sector have positive effect on economic growth of Iraq during the reviewed period.

7. Okwuosa et al (2023) evaluated the impact of financial deepening on commercial bank performance in Nigeria using a time series data of 22 years covering 2000 to 2022. Financial deepening indicators included in the study were credit allocation to private sector as a ratio of GDP, money supply as a ratio of GDP and total loan to deposit ratio while net interest margin was used

as proxy for commercial bank performance.

The Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test was used in determining stationarity of the data and auto regressive distributed lag model was used in the empirical analysis. The results affirm a unidirectional relationship between credit allocated to private sector ratio to GDP and net interest margin why no causality was found between other variables. The study recommends CBN to adopt policies that will assist or encourage commercial banks to improve on their financial deepening activities so as to broaden their financial services operations

8. Okafor et al, (2021) investigated the relationship between financial deepening and economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1986 to 2016. The study used financial deepening indicators of credit to the private sector as a ratio to GDP, the percentage of market capitalization to GDP, and real GDP. The study adopted Johanssen Cointegration, error correction, and granger causality for the empirical analysis. The study concludes that financial deepening is positive and significantly impacts economic growth in

Nigeria within the reviewed period.

9. Samuel-Hope et al, (2020) conducted a study on the influence of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 – 2018. The study used financial deepening indicators of bank's time and savings deposits, credit to the private sector as a ratio of GDP, money supply as a ratio of GDP, and real GDP. The study used Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) as a method of data analysis. The result shown the existence of a long-run relationship but none of the regressors was significant. The study recommends favorable policies for lending to the private sector.

10. Nwaolisa and Cyril (2019) explored the impact of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data spanning 1990 – 2016. The study adopted financial deepening indicators of stock market capitalization, money supply, and private sector credit. The method of empirical analysis was the ordinary least square (OLS). The study affirmed that all the financial deepening variables have positive impact on economic growth. The study recommends minimizing liquidity barriers in the stock market, removing constraints

in international markets and improving capacity in bank lending.

11. Akinmulegun & Akinde, (2019) examined the link between financial deepening and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1981-2017 using time series data. The study adopted error correction method (ECM) to carry out the empirical analysis. Financial deepening indicators used by the study include: credit to private sector, market capitalization, value of transaction and interest rate, while manufacturing sector performance was proxy by manufacturing value added to GDP. The finding revealed that credit to private sector and market capitalization positively affects manufacturing sector performance while value of transaction and interest rate negatively affect manufacturing sector performance.

3. 12. Maxwell & Oluwatosin (2012) evaluated the impact of financial deepening on manufacturing output in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010. The study used the vector autoregressive (VAR) technique to carry out the empirical analysis. The findings show that the financial deepening indicators' coefficients do not

significantly influence manufacturing output in Nigeria

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

William M.K. Trochim (2001) defines research design as the overall plan or strategy for conducting research. This study adopts the ex-post facto research design as it deals with outcome of an event that have already occurred and the data of interest were readily available for collection. Growth in manufacturing sector was use as the dependent variables, while financial deepening indicators of financial depth, financial access and financial efficiency were employ as the independent variables. The empirical analysis of the model was done using Auto Regressive Distributed lag. Time series data of a sample period of thirty three years was use. The unit root test was conducted using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.

3.2 Data Collection

Data of variables of interest which is data on growth in Manufacturing was obtained from World Bank Development Indicators (WDI). While data on the major indicators of financial deepening of financial depth,

financial access and financial efficiency were sourced from CBN Statistical

Bulletins from 1990-2023 and used for the empirical analysis.

S/N	VARIABLES	SOURCES	PERIOD
1	Financial Depth	CBN Statistical Bulletin	1990 -2023
2	Financial Access	CBN Statistical Bulletin	1990 -2023
3	Financial Efficiency	CBN Statistical Bulletin	1990 -2023
4	Growth in Manufacturing Sector	World Bank Development Indicators(WDI)	1990 -2023

Key: WDI/CBN Statistical Bulletin and various issues

3.3 Model Specification

The functional link between the dependent variable and the independent variables of this study is anchored on the theory of supply leading hypothesis by Schumpeter (1911) and expressed in conjunction with the analytical framework of Okeke, I. C. & Akunna, R. C. (2023) and Nwaolisa and Cyril (2019) who carried out a study on the effect of financial deepening on Nigeria economic growth using ratio of money supply to GDP, insurance premiums to GDP, stock market capitalization to GDP and private sector credit to GDP as indicators of financial deepening. However, in this study, modification was done by extending the scope and includes other variables like growth in manufacturing sector (GMS), financial depth (FD) financial access (FA), and financial efficiency (FE) that is:

$$GMS = f (FD, FA, FE) \quad (3.1)$$

The generalized ARDL Regression Model is specified as:

$$Y_t = a_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + a_j Y_{t-j} + \beta_0 X_t + \beta_k X_{t-j} + e_t \quad (3.2)$$

The time series is represented by $t = 1, 2, \dots, 33$ and it goes from 1990 to 2023. Y_t represents the endogenous variable (GMS) and, j is the maximum lag length chosen. Consequently, the ARDL Specification for the study is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} GMS \\ = \alpha_i + \beta_1 FD_{t-j} + \beta_2 FA_{t-j} + \beta_3 FE_{t-j} \\ + \epsilon_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Since there is co-integration among the variables, the error correction form of model 3.3 is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GMS_t = & \delta + \sum_{i=1}^p a_1 \Delta FD_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^q a_2 \Delta FA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q a_3 \Delta FE_{t-i} + \\ & \&ECT_{t-i} + \\ & e_t \end{aligned}$$

Where: $GMS =$

Growth in Manufacturing Sector as dependent variable **FD** = Financial Depth, **FA** = Financial Access and **FE** = Financial Efficiency (all serving as regressors). α = speed of adjustment (with a negative sign, it shows convergence, while positive sign is lack of convergence).

$\alpha_1 - \alpha_3$ are short run coefficients, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ captures long run relationships, δ represents the intercept or constant, μ is the error term and Δ represents the difference operator. The a priori expectations require that increase in financial depth; increase in financial access and increase in financial efficiency will lead to increase in growth in the manufacturing sector of the economy. The symbolic representations of the relationship based on the a priori expectations are as follows: $b_1 > 0$, $b_2 > 0$, and $b_3 > 0$,

3.4 Method and Techniques of Data Analysis

This study used auto regressive distributive lag (ARDL) method developed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) to carry out the empirical analysis between financial deepening and

manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria. ARDL technique was chosen because of its unique quality of being able to analyze variables when all the dataset for analysis are not all stationary and also when there is tendency of mixed order of integration among the variables. The study made use of time series data which necessitated stationarity tests. Successively, the Unit Root Test was conducted and it was followed by the co-integration test to examine whether long run relationship exist among variables of financial deepening. The study used the Augmented Dickey and Fuller (1981) approach to test for the unit root of the variables and also to ascertain their respective order of integration. Presence of unit root in the data necessitated the application of the bound cointegration test as proposed by Pesaro, Shin and Smith (2001) to establish whether the variables have long-run relationship. The study found a long run relationship among the variables, which implies that they can be combined in a linear form and in the event of shock or disturbance in the short run they would converge with time in the long run.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

**4.1.1 Trend Analysis of Financial Manufacturing sector Growth in Nigeria
Sector Deepening Indicators and Nigeria**

extracted from the WDI

Source: Author’s Computation based on data

Source: Author’s Computation based on data extracted from the WDI

The descriptive analysis of the trends of the variables shows that the growth of manufacturing sector depicted Figure 4.1, witnessed a decrease from 1990 to

1993 before increasing to 3.2% in 1996. It fluctuated between 1998 and 2002 at a declining rate. It attained a record low of (-14%) in 1995 and a record high of 22% in 2013. Since then, the sector has been growing at a decreasing rate. The trends of financial access showed in Figure 4.2 indicates that it witnessed continuous

increase from 1990 to 1996 before maintain a constant growth till 2008. It declined significantly from 2008 and become maximized of 0.5% in rest of the period to 2023. Financial depth depicted also in Figure 4.2 witness an increase between 1990 and 1996. It attained a record low of 0.05% in 1998 and a record high of 0.11% in 2007. it fluctuated between 2010 and 2018 before rising to

witnessing continuous increase up till 2023. Lastly, financial efficiency depicted in Figure 4.2 fluctuated between 1990 and 2023. It witnessed a record low of 0.45% in 2011 and became maximize of 0.65% in 2022.

4.1.2 Basic Descriptive Statistics Result

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of the series

	MANUFACTURING SECTOR GROWTH	FINANCIAL ACCESS	FINANCIAL DEPTH	FINANCIAL EFFICIENCY
Mean	2.258888	0.465054	0.047055	0.517814
Median	2.198512	0.501671	0.049966	0.500196
Maximum	21.7971	0.507519	0.111617	0.654383
Minimum	-17.5105	0.264885	0.015215	0.387831
Std. Dev.	8.734068	0.073115	0.022367	0.082776
Skewness	0.060762	-1.76507	0.266168	0.14377
Kurtosis	3.309081	4.596733	3.228368	1.720566
Jarque-Bera	0.156257	21.26612	0.475339	2.436144
Probability	0.924846	0.000024	0.788463	0.2958
Sum	76.8022	15.81182	1.599873	17.60568
Sum Sq. Dev.	2517.37	0.176409	0.016509	0.22611
Observations	34	34	34	34

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

From Table 4.1, it was noted that growth in manufacturing sector averaged 2.26 % between 1990 and 2023. The minimum and maximum values of growth in manufacturing sector are 21.8% and -17.5 % respectively. Financial access

ranged between 0.3% and 0.5%, while financial depth ranged from 0.02% to 0.1% and financial efficiency averaged 0.05% between 1990 and 2023 and ranged from 0.38% to 0.65%. In addition to this, the probability values of the Jarque-Bera statistics of all the variables exclusive of financial access are more

than 5%, indicating that at 5% level, the errors in the variables are normally distributed.

4.2 Data Analysis

This section contains the pre-estimation diagnostics tests and estimated cointegration models in addition to the associated post-estimation tests.

4.2.1 Pre-estimation Diagnostics Tests (Multicollinearity Test)

The multicollinearity test for this study was done using variance inflation factor. The VIF coefficients are reported in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Variance Inflation Factor coefficient

	Coefficient	Uncentered	Centered
Variable	Variance	VIF	VIF
FINANCIAL_ACCESS	51.65099	60.88737	1.426488
FINANCIAL_DEPTH	671.0295	9.642966	1.73433
FINANCIAL_EFFICIENCY	57.21897	83.69018	2.025478
MANUFACTURING_GROWTH	0.00268	1.128848	1.056068

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Table 4.2 shows the centered variance inflation factor coefficients for the variables. It was noted that the model is free from multicollinearity as the centered variance inflation factor coefficients for each of the variables is not too high (i.e. value of VIF <5). It therefore follows that

the independent variables can be regressed together without problem of uncertain coefficients and high variance.

4.2.2 Unit Root Test

The unit root test results are summarized in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of ADF unit root test results

ADF Unit root test results					
Variable	Levels test results		First Difference test results		
	t-stat.	5% critical value	t-stat.	5% critical value	Order of integration
GMS	-1.81	-3.56	-4.25	-3.56	I(1)
FA	-3.03	-2.97	-3.45	-3.56	I(0)

FD	-3.17	-3.56	-6.06	-3.56	I(1)
FE	-1.43	-2.97	-5.29	-3.56	I(1)

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Table 4.3 shown the unit test results for each of the variables. The leftmost part shows the test results at levels while the rightmost part shows the test results at first difference. It was establish that all the variables are stationary at first difference except financial access that is stationary at level. The unit root result

shows that the variables are mixed integrated and thus, can enter into the ARDL model upon verification of long run relationship via the cointegration test.

4.2.3 Cointegration Test

The Bound test proposed by Pesaro, Shin and Smith (2001) methodology was applied.

Table 4.4: Bound results for model Agricultural model

Series: GMS, FA FD FE				
F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis	LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND
		No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value OF	SIGNIFICANT	I(0)	I(1)
	F-stat			
F-statistic	8.104056	10%	3.47	4.45
K	3	5%	4.01	5.07
		2.5%	4.52	5.62
		1%	5.17	6.36

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

The bound test result of growth in Manufacturing shows that the variables

have long run relationship as the F-statistics value is greater than the 0.05 critical value of the upper bound.

4.3 Estimation of the Cointegration

Model

The cointegration models that portray the long run behavior of the variables are estimated using Auto regressive distributive lag (ARDL) model with the specification of both the short and long run short forms of equation results.

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Table 4.5: ARDL SHORT AND LONG RUN (MODEL ONE): GMS

Table 4.5 shows the ARDL regression

Short Run Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GMS(-1))	-0.160023	0.135815	-1.178240	0.2598
D(FIN_ACC)	281.5261	76.12171	3.698368	0.0027
D(FIN_DEP)	-46.55243	80.67109	-0.577065	0.5738
D(FIN_DEP(-1))	-374.3760	89.29000	-4.192810	0.0011
D(FIN_DEP(-2))	-320.5214	71.45834	-4.485431	0.0006
D(FIN__EFF_)	69.36624	35.83364	1.935785	0.0749
D(FIN__EFF_(-1))	64.27036	28.25863	2.274363	0.0405
D(FIN__EFF_(-2))	67.20898	26.71983	2.515323	0.0258
CointEq(-1)*	-0.874347	0.135540	-6.450829	0.0000
R-squared	0.830964	Mean dependent var		0.630503
Adjusted R-squared	0.693621	S.D. dependent var		8.902327
S.E. of regression	4.927570	Akaike info criterion		6.332294
Sum squared resid	388.4951	Schwarz criterion		6.986186
Log likelihood	-80.98440	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.541479
Durbin-Watson stat	1.973626			

Long Run Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FIN_ACC	74.23726	28.59933	2.595769	0.0222
FIN_DEP	466.5654	175.5954	2.657047	0.0197
FIN__EFF_	-106.4142	38.74888	-2.746253	0.0167

results for the growth in manufacturing model. The result affirms that financial

access and depth have positive significant effect on growth in the manufacturing sector. This finding agrees with the a priori expectation that increase in financial access and financial depth as an indicators of financial deepening will lead to growth in the manufacturing sector. Financial efficiency was found to exert negative significant effect on growth in manufacturing sector. The coefficient of determination (R²) reveals that the proportion of the explained variation to the total variations in growth in manufacturing model is 0.83. This shows that the explanatory power of the regressors is 83 percent. Thus, the

model is considered as a good fit as the observations, on the average converge to the regression. The ARDL Short run result shows that the coefficient of the error correction term (COINTEQ01) is -0.874347. The result is negative and significant at the 5% level of statistical significance meaning that 87.4% of the discrepancy from the long-run equilibrium is corrected each period.

4.4: Post-estimation Diagnostics Tests

The post-diagnostic test includes the, serial correlation LM test, normality test and stability test.

Table: 4.6 Autocorrelation test result for Manufacturing model

Autocorrelation test result for Growth in Manufacturing Model				
Dependent Variable =GMS				
F-statistic	2.02893	Prob. F(2,28)		0.15
Obs*R-squared	4.303694	Prob. Chi-Square(2)		0.116
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FIN_ACC	4.538089	24.51154	0.185141	0.855
FIN_DEP	41.36549	91.76219	0.45079	0.656
FIN__EFF_	-15.5497	25.83362	-0.60192	0.552
C	3.970195	12.4715	0.318341	0.753
RESID(-1)	0.381619	0.194074	1.966361	0.059
RESID(-2)	-0.01907	0.19198	-0.09932	0.922

R-squared	0.126579	Mean dependent var	-9.40E-16
Adjusted R-squared	-0.02939	S.D. dependent var	8.586
S.E. of regression	8.710794	Akaike info criterion	7.326
Sum squared resid	2124.582	Schwarz criterion	7.595
Log likelihood	-118.538	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.418
F-statistic	0.811572	Durbin-Watson stat	2.007
Prob(F-statistic)	0.55141		

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

The serial correlation LM test in Table 4.6 shows that growth in manufacturing

model is free from serial correlation at 5% level.

Figure 4.3: Plot of normality test for manufacturing model

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

From the normality test results illustrated in figure 4.3 the errors in the models is normally distributed. This is because the associated probability value of the

Jarque-Bera statistics is greater than 5%.

Table: 4.7: Stability Test Result for Manufacturing Model

The Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of squares serves as the stability test.

This is represented in the figure below:

As shown in Table 4.7, the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of Squares line is within the 5% critical value bounds. Therefore, the estimate of the long-run model for Manufacturing is stable.

5.1 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main aim of the study was to explore the effect of financial deepening on manufacturing growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1990 and 2023. The study used manufacturing sector growth as explanatory variable while financial deepening indicators of financial depth, financial access and financial efficiency as independent variables. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) result reveals that all the independent variables have positive significant relationship with growth in Manufacturing, except financial efficiency.

From the ARDL result, inference can be drawn that financial deepening has significant impact on manufacturing growth in Nigeria during the studied period. Hence, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Financial inclusion driven policy should be implement by monetary authorities in Nigeria so that majority of the citizenry will have easy access to affordable financial services that will impact positively in the manufacturing sector, therefore leading to economic growth.

2. CBN should adopt financial depth driven policy so as to encourage banks to increase lending to the manufacturing sector in order to boost manufacturing output in the country.

a. And uphold trade-related regulations.

b. Adopt laws and initiatives that promote economic diversification, industrialization, and value addition. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) should get focused assistance in order to improve their competitiveness and their ability to engage in intra-African trade.

Encourage member nations to harmonize their standards, technical regulations, and conformity assessment practices. This will lower trade obstacles pertaining to product quality and safety by fostering compatibility and mutual recognition.

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